

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 6.3

Plans for Provision for Open-Source Software

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Deliverable 6.3

Plans for provision of open-source software

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Partner abbreviations

Full name

NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
HI	Háskóli Íslands (University of Iceland)
LOBA	Loba (Portugal)
CHX	Crowd Helix (Ireland)
SVEN	Smart Venice (Italy)
DIGI	Digiotouch (Estonia)
ULEID	Leiden University (The Netherlands)
FARPL	Farplas Automotive (Türkiye)
BFH	Bern University of Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

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Abbreviations

OSS

Meaning

Open-Source Software

1 Executive Summary

The BIAS project is committed to demonstrate a proof-of-concept of an ethical, transparent AI powered recruitment and engagement with the European AI community for wider take up of its results. This deliverable reports about BIAS project's plans provision of open source software. It introduces two primary software components for open source release: (i) a bias detection and mitigation tool for word embeddings and (ii) a Decision Support System for fair recruitment decision-making. Together, these tools advance BIAS's goal of trustworthy, socially responsible AI, aligning with European open-source principles to benefit the broader AI powered recruitment ecosystems.

2 Introduction

The EU-funded BIAS project is dedicated to fundamentally transform how AI-powered recruitment solutions are developed and operated in Europe. One of the main goals of the project is to demonstrate a proof-of-concept Debiaser, which is socially responsible and transparent as well as aligns with the ethical principles and European regulatory frameworks. For a much wider impact creation and fostering AI community involvement, further innovation, and operational sustainability, BIAS partners are committed to releasing selected project outcomes (mainly software outcomes) as open source. This approach will enable widespread access to cutting-edge, responsible AI technology, encouraging collaborative improvements and broader adoption beyond the conclusion of the project.

The deliverable D6.3 outlines the preliminary strategy for open-source software developed in the BIAS project. It covers an initial roadmap, open-source licensing considerations, and the relevant software components. This public deliverable has been planned to complement the confidential (initial) business plan presented in D6.2.

2.1 Motivation

The motivation behind the project's open-source approach and deliverable aligns directly with the European Commission's commitment to a "Think Open" approach¹, promoting the openness, transparency, and collaboration necessary for a digitally sovereign Europe. While some of the BIAS outcomes will be kept confidential for filing two patents,² the rest of the outcomes will be released with an open-source license. By sharing BIAS-developed software components openly, the partners will empower diverse stakeholders (e.g., AI developers, product owners, AI researchers) to access and contribute to further improvement on the Debiaser technology, ensuring that it remains trustworthy, socially responsible, transparent, interoperable, and adaptable. It is anticipated to foster collective innovation towards trustworthy AI in Europe. This open-source release further ensures that the proof-of-concept of the Debiaser-powered AI recruitment platform will remain sustainable and beneficial to the broader European AI community. It will also reduce barriers for new entrants to high-quality digital resources and supporting an ethical, community-driven AI-powered digital landscape.

2.2 Deliverable organisation

This deliverable is organised as follows. Section 1 provides the executive summary, while Section 2 introduces the deliverable along with its motivation. Section 3 outlines the proposed tools that are planned to be released with an open source license. Section 4 concludes the report.

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/digital-services/open-source-software-strategy_en

² An initial indication of patents was provided in Deliverable D6.1.

3 Open Source Software Components

This section outlines two main software components which are proposed to be released with open source licenses. Since they are in early stages of development, more detailed descriptions will be provided in the final version of this deliverable D6.7. Also, the scope of the components may evolve as the project progresses and they are validated with the end user.

3.1 Bias detection and mitigation in word embeddings

This module will be developed by BFH in WP3. It involves identifying and reducing unintended biases within language models, especially within the mathematical representations of words, known as word embeddings. They capture relationships between words based on context, but they can also inherit social and cultural biases from the training data. Detecting such bias requires analysing these embeddings for patterns that might unfairly associate certain words or groups. Mitigation techniques then adjust the embeddings to minimise biased associations, fostering fairer AI applications. In addition to the source code, BFH will produce word lists and scientific publication as outcomes, all of which will be published as open source (with Apache 2.0 or CC-BY-4.0 license). Preliminary results have already been published in a public Github repository³ and an Arxiv technical report⁴

3.2 Decision support system

This is a decision support system (DSS) in the recruitment process to make fair decisions and will be developed jointly by BFH and NTNU. It corresponds to the definition of justice and development of a justice metric adapted to the recruitment domain and includes data collection from different sources, including data from HR staff's notes and evaluation results during the application process and data from the NLP component. A case will be created for each application and the CBR will be populated with these cases. The DSS is planned to be integrated within memotive.app, a company under Farplas and/or Farplas will utilise the DSS for its own internal recruitment tool during the validation task T6.4. In addition to the source code, BFH and NTNU will produce scientific publication as outcomes, all of which will be published as open source (with Apache 2.0 or CC-BY-4.0 license).

³ <https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS>

⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2407.18689>

4 Conclusions

D6.3 summarises two key software components of BIAS which are planned to be released as open source. Their development is ongoing, and validation is planned to be done in Task T6.4 during the final year of the project. Furthermore, in Month 48 (October 2026), a final open-source software strategy report will be drawn up describing the specific software components released, provide links to code repositories, and reflect on the community's engagement with these resources. Together, these deliverables will support the BIAS project's goal of enabling trustworthy and fair AI innovation through open-source components for the wider European AI communities and public interest.

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